

Google IT Automation certificate program

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Course 1:

- We learn the programming language syntax and semantics, to know how to tell the computer what to do exactly.
- Automation: is the process of replacing a manual step with one that can happen automatically.
- Uses of automation:
 - o The automatic timing and regulation of traffic lights
 - o A repetitive task that is at high risk for human error
 - o Sending commands to a computer
 - o Detecting and removing duplicates of data
 - o Sending automated emails that are personalized by pulling individual names from a database and plugging them into the email
 - o Updating a large number of file permissions
 - o Reporting on system data, like disk or memory usage
 - o Installing software
 - o Generating reports
 - o Deploying a file or a computer program to all computers on a company network
 - o Using a configuration management system to deploy software patches, after a human has *designed* the system
 - o Populating an e-commerce site with products
 - o Setting the home directory and access permissions for users
- Programming code may also be referred to as source code or scripts.
- Programming languages are similar to human spoken languages in that they both use syntax and semantics.
- Syntax is a set of rules for how statements are constructed in both human and computer languages.
- Semantics refers to the intended meaning or effect of statements, or collections of words, in both human and computer languages.
- Scripts are usually shorter and less complex than computer programs. Scripts are often used to automate specific tasks.
- There are platform specific programming languages, like “bash” for Linux and “PowerShell” for windows.
- “Perl” and “ruby” are languages used for scripting and automation.
- Also “JavaScript” is a widely used language
- **Python is:**
 - o a general purpose scripting language;
 - o a popular language used to code a variety of applications;
 - o a frequently used tool for automation;
 - o a cross-platform compatible language;

- a beginner-friendly language.
- **Python is not:**
 - a platform-specific / OS-specific scripting language;
 - a client-side scripting language;
 - a purely object-oriented programming language.
- **Client-side scripting language** - Client-side scripting languages, like JavaScript, are used mostly for web programming. The scripts are transferred from a web server to the end-user's internet browser, then executed in the browser.
- "echo" == "print()" in bash and python respectively
- When using the "print()" function and including a string and an integer in the argument, make sure to cast the integer into a string explicitly, because the arguments need to be from the same type. And that is so for better look and overall. And it could work without it.
- Some terms to know when writing functions:
 - **return value** - the value or variable returned as the end result of a function
 - **parameter (argument)** - a value passed into a function for use within the function
 - **refactoring code** - a process to restructure code without changing functionality, to increase readability and make it easier to reuse.
- Best practices for writing code that is readable and reusable:
 - **Create a reusable function** - Replace duplicate code with one reusable function to make the code easier to read and repurpose.
 - **Refactor code** - Update code so that it is self-documenting and the intent of the code is clear.
 - **Add comments** - Adding comments is part of creating self-documenting code. Using comments allows you to leave notes to yourself and/or other programmers to make the purpose of the code clear.
- You can use the comparison operators (" $<$ ", " $>$ ", " $==$ ") to compare strings, where each string has a Unicode number and when comparing the values of the unicodes gets added and compared as any other integers.
- If you want to know the values of the Unicode use ("ord()") function.
- **Branching:** is the ability of a program to alter its execution sequence.
- The escape character "\" in Python allows "illegal" characters to be used in a string, like the apostrophe (\').
- Code that is written so that it is readable and doesn't conceal its intent is called self-documenting code
- **For loops** maybe used to:
 - Copy files to machines
 - Process the contents of files
 - Automatically install software
- Recursion is about summing the current variable with the same function for the "variable - 1"
- Using the ".format" method we can reorder the variables between the curly braces. And for

Formatting expressions

Expr	Meaning	Example
{:d}	integer value	'{:d}'.format(10.5) → '10'
{:.2f}	floating point with that many decimals	'{:2f}'.format(0.5) → '0.50'
{:.2s}	string with that many characters	'{:2s}'.format('Python') → 'Py'
{:<6s}	string aligned to the left that many spaces	'{:<6s}'.format('Py') → 'Py '
{:>6s}	string aligned to the right that many spaces	'{:>6s}'.format('Py') → ' Py'
{:^6s}	string centered in that many spaces	'{:^6s}'.format('Py') → ' Py '

- Enumerate functions makes things easier when trying to get the even and odd elements of a list.
- Dictionary values can be any data types, but dictionary keys must be one of the following:
 - o Numbers
 - o Booleans
 - o Tuples
 - o Strings
- In OOP an object may have:
 - o The attributes are the characteristics associated to a type, such as an apple color or taste.
 - o The methods are the functions associated to a type, such as an apple cut or eat.
- To get the methods associated with a data type (int, str,...) we may use: “dir()” and when we use it we will have so many Dunder methods at the beginning that gets used by the interpreter when performing different operation or such.
- Also, you can use the help() function to find more about the data type class.

- Variables that have different names in different objects are called **instance variables**.
- Adding a docstring to a class or a function it makes it easier to understand code by you or for someone who is reusing it, and the docstrings contents gets displayed when you use “help()”
- Another type of code reuse besides the inheritance is the “**composition**” which means using a class inside of another class without having a child parent relationship meaning there will be no inheritance between them, and the example used is when using a dictionary in the definition of a class while, I think there is a possibility o use a user-defined class inside of another class. And the thought got confirmed, IT IS POSSIBLE.
- It looks from the example code used in the videos, that “dictionaries” are the best data structure to be used in controlling servers and accounts databases.

Course 2: Using python to interact with operating system

- The operating system is a program that talks to the machine on one side to manage the system resources, disk, memory, and network.
- On the other side the kernel talks to the user space, user interface, and system’s programs
- The term “operating system” means both the kernel and the user space.
- A compiled language like (C, C++, Go, Rust) uses a compiler which translates the code into machine level program, that will make the compiled program much faster to execute but the compiling process could take time.
- On the other hand, there is the interpreted programming language like (Python, Ruby, JavaScript, Bash, PowerShell) which does not need a compiler and the interpreter does all the work to get the output by understanding the code written.
- And some languages like (Java, C#) uses a mixed approach, since the code gets compiled into an intermediate code and not into a machine language code and that makes it work on different platforms when using a specific program like (JVM) for Java, while machine code compilation make it require a specific operating system.
- There is a command named “shebang” Inserting a shebang line (such as **#!/usr/bin/env python3**) as the first line tells the operating system what command we want to use to execute the script.
- When working on a (for example: library) you should put your files in a directory and make all the files executable and include a (`__init__.py`) file in the directory for the interpreter to understand that it is a module directory.
- Automation is useful for:
 - o Scalability, Scalability means that when more work is added to a system, the system can do whatever it needs to complete the work.
 - o Centralizing mistakes
 - o Saving time
- To find out whether it is useful to automate a certain task or not we could use the following equation:

$\text{time_to_automate} < (\text{time_to_perform} * \text{amount_of_times_done})$

- the Pareto Principle: states that 20% of the system administration tasks that you perform are responsible for 80% of your work.
 - Bit-rot: This process of software falling out of step with the environment is sometimes.
 - Automation has a **Forensic-Value**, which means that the automation enables us to spot failures and to debug the process by saving Logs
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- In Linux the **absolute path** is the path starting from the “/home/user” directory and ending in the directory wanted. And the **relative path** is the path starting from the current directory and ending in the directory wanted.
 - The readline() method reads a single line from the current position, the read() method reads from the current position until the end of the file.
 - If you open a file for writing that already exists, the contents of the file will be deleted as soon as it is opened.
 - “os” module is cross-platform module but we need to pay attention to the path, of the file if the system get changed the path too.
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- The modules learn on so far are “os” “shutil” “psutil”
 - Parsing means analyzing the file content to correctly structure the data.
 - We use regular expressions to recognize patterns in a string.
 - String.index() like re.search() like for command-line grep -I string where all of them find a certain text in a piece of string
 - Standard I/O streams in python has three types:
 - o STDIN: such as input()
 - o STDOUT: such as print()
 - o STDERR: such as SyntaxError
 - There is other shells besides “Bash” such as “Zsh”, “Fish”
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- “subprocess” module is used to execute the command-line commands from python.
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- **A unit test** is a test of the smallest testable piece of the software.
 - **Automatic testing** is Codifying tests into its own software and code that can be run to verify that our programs do what we expect them to do.
 - **It is bad for automation to fail silently.**
 - There are two **types** of software testing:

- White-box test (clear-box or transparent testing): this test relies on the test creator's knowledge of the software being tested to construct the test cases. In this case the test is written before or alongside the software.
- Black-box tests: are written with an awareness of what the program is supposed to do – its requirements or specifications – but not how it does it. And here probably the test is written before the software is.
- **Integration testing** is to verify that the interactions between the different pieces of code in integrated environments are working the way we expect them to. One of its test cases is taking the different units tested by the automatic test and verify that they all work as a whole
- **Regression tests.** They're usually written as part of a debugging and troubleshooting process to verify that an issue or error has been fixed once it's been identified.
- **Smoke test** sometimes called build verification test, serve as a kind of sanity check to find major bugs in a program. Smoke test answer basic questions like, does the program run? These tests are usually run before more refined testing takes place. get their name from a concept that comes from testing hardware equipment. Plug in the given piece of hardware and see if smoke starts coming out of it.
- **Load tests** are tests verify that the system behaves well when it's under significant load.
- Taking together a group of tests of one or many kinds is commonly referred to as a **test suite**.
- A process called **test-driven development** or TDD calls for creating the test before writing the code.
- When engineers submit their code, it's integrated into the main repository and tests are automatically run against it to spot bugs and errors in a process called **Continuous Integration**.
- Course 2 week 5 has so many new stuff.

- In bash we can redirect streams using the “>” to save the out put of a command into another file, and “>>” to append the output to a file, and “<” to read the contents of a file.
- And another redirection technique is called piping or pipelining

- Using keyboard shortcuts like “Ctrl+C” and “Ctrl+D” to finish processes, is called signaling

Course 3: Introduction to git and GitHub

- Version control system (VCS): is useful in:
 - Rolling back when something wrong happens
 - Collaborate with others
- Git is a “distributed version control system”.
- When you are creating a new script to replace an old one, and after running it you find that it is buggy, it is preferred for you roll-back to the old version that is not buggy, then complete fixing the new version, then start using the new one.

- Some of the commands for finding the differences between files (diff, wdiff, meld, vimdiff)
- After using the diff command, you can redirect the output to a new file with extension “.diff”

And then you can use “patch” to apply the changes in the “.diff” file to the new file

- A commit is treating a group of edits as a single change.
- Git is powerful because it gives full access to repositories to a huge number of developers.
- The “git directory” is where the older versions and the files history is kept and the “working tree” is where the current file are kept, and the ones being worked on.
- “Staging area” is where the changes are kept until it gets committed.
- In git files are either “tracked” or “untracked” and to track a file we use “git add” this command will move it from untracked to staged.
 - o Tracked files are either: “modified” or “staged” or “committed”
- A short description of the change (up to 50 characters), followed by one or more paragraphs giving more details of the change

In short how git works is:

- Use config to give the identity.
- Initialize git in a directory
- Create and edit stuff
- Add them to be tracked and staged
- Commit the staged stuff

In the commands above there is many flags such as “-a” that will allow to add the change while committing without the need for staging

- The “HEAD” alias is given to the latest commit in the branch
- Flags for “git commit” and “git log” are many and we can use “git show” to check a commit in more depth after getting the ID from “git log”
- “Git diff” is the command to use when looking for the changes that happened to a file before committing
- “git rm” is to untrack and delete a file.
- “git mv” to rename files
- If we want to add an exception to the output of the “git status” we can create a “.gitignore” file to the git directory and include the files that are not relevant in this file.
- “git checkout” is a command for discarding changes that has happened for a file, and restoring the previous commit state, or switch branches.
- “git reset” is for undo file staging.
- ***git commit --amend*** allows us to modify and add changes to the most recent commit. But using it on public repos could lead to confusing situations
- “git revert” will rollback by creating a commit contains the same state of the older commit
- Git uses the crypto “SHA1” to name the commits not for security reasons but to avoid collision, so it could be used by using only the first few characters.

- a **branch** at the most basic level is just a pointer to a particular commit. But more importantly, it represents an independent line of development in a project. Of which the commit it points to is the latest link in a chain of developing history.
- Use branches in the form of test environment and when you have a success, merge the successful result to the master branch.
- When using “git branch” we use “checkout” to change our work from one branch to another
- “merge” is to join the branched work with the history of work and after merging the two merged branches point at the same commit.
- Git uses two merging algorithms:
 - o Fast-forward: when two branches that have different histories merge.
 - o Three-way merge: when a branch splits from the master and merge into it.
- “git config --global credential.helper cache” is a command that allows us to save the GitHub credentials to automatically log in in the future.
- If we want to change a remote branch we must Pull the remote branch, merge it with the local branch, then push it back to its origin.
- The difference between the “merge” and “pull” commands is that fetch gets a remote copy, and you need to manually merge after it, while pull = “fetch” + “merge”
- “fast-forward” is for changes without conflicts
- Explicit merge will create a merge commit when merging in contrast to implicit merge
- To understand the logs, we could use the command “git log --graph --oneline --all”
- git rebase refactor Move the current branch on top of the refactor branch, and we can consider rebase as an alternative to merge.

Best practices for collaborating with others:

- It's a good idea to always synchronize your branches before starting any work on your own.
- try and avoid having very large changes that modify a lot of different things. Instead, try to make changes as small as possible as long as they're self-contained.
- push your changes often and pull before doing any work.
- regularly merge changes made on the master branch back onto the feature branch.
- have the latest version of the project in the master branch and a stable version of the project on a separate branch.
- having good commit messages is important.
- Forking is a way of creating a copy of the given repository so that it belongs to our user. And we can commit changes and the workflow for forking is:
 - o Create a fork of the repo and work on it locally.
 - o Merge the fork to the original repo by creating a “Pull Request”
- pull request is a commit or series of commits that you send to the owner of the repository so that they incorporate it into their tree. Or sometimes it is just a simple edit to a developer's code you send it to in order correct or improve their code.

- code review means going through someone else's code, documentation or configuration and checking that it all makes sense and follows the expected patterns.
- continuous integration system will build and test our code every time there's a change.
- Continuous Delivery means new code is often deployed with the goal of avoiding rollouts with lots of changes between two versions.
- Artifacts can include compiled code, test results, logs, or any type of file generated as part of the pipeline.

Course4:

- Troubleshooting: is the process of identifying, analyzing and solving problems.
- Debugging: is the process of identifying, analyzing and removing bugs in the system.
- To troubleshoot networks: use tcpdump, Wireshark
- To check system resources: use ps, top, free
- To look system calls or library calls made by a program or a library we use (respectively): strace, ltrace
- Problem solving steps:
 - o Gather information, “reproduction case” is super important
 - o Finding the root cause
 - o Performing the necessary remediation
- System calls are calls the program running on our computer makes to the running memory. Check the internet to learn how to read the different system calls files
- **Less:** command is a linux terminal pager that shows one page at a time.
- Issue reporting form questions:
 - o What were you trying to do?
 - o What steps did you follow?
 - o What was the expected result?
 - o What was the actual result?
- A reproduction case is to verify if the problem is present or not.
 - o Look into the syslog.
 - o Look for similar cases or when things get repeated and when it does not.
 - o Try other versions of the program.
 - o Check the ltrace and strace.
 - o Ask for help about the application
- Most of the time the reproduction case will not show the root cause, but finding the root cause is essential for our long-term solution
- Finding the root cause comes from our creativity in problem solving and when there is not enough information, we do more research or look up the program documentation online or other things.
- Whenever possible use the test environment instead of the production environment for hypothesis check

- There are some commands that could help about the I/O from the disk such as (“iotop”, “vmstat”, “iostat”, “ionice”, “iftop”)
- We can use the “rsync” to backup or “trickle” to limit the bandwidth being used.
- To find the root cause use any of the ways above and keep trying with any of them until you find the root cause.
- Enable the debugging mode in the application or service.
- When we run into a bug we might want to investigate:
 - o The load on the computer
 - o The processes running at the same time
 - o The usage of the network
- You might run into a “Heisenbug” which is extra hard to understand because it follows the observer effect, which is usually point to bad resource management.

The observer effect is “just observing the phenomenon alters the phenomenon”

- If you cannot find the cause of the issue with all of that, try turning thing on and off until it shows.
- Linear search: means searching the information from the start to the end one by one.
- Binary search: look into the middle of the information and keep the half that contain the needed result and delete the other half
- When the binary search applied to the IT trouble shooting it is called “bisecting” and it gets applied by, for example: when an application crash, we look-up half of the files of the group that caused the crash and put off the half that runs, then split the crashing part into half and put off the running half, then keep going until we find the single file that causes the issue.
- “git bisect” is a command for applying binary search to a GitHub repository.

Slowness:

- The general strategy to identify slowness is to identify the bottleneck that is causing the slowness
- First look if there is a certain application causing the slowness and if non look if there is a resource exhaustion. And the third possible reason one of the programs may have a memory leak
- If you are getting some data from the network, try to cache it on the local hard disk to make things easier for reusage in the future
- A cache stores data in a form that is faster to access than its original form such as a web proxy, DNS

- When the computer runs out of RAM it will start deleting unused data and if it keeps being full it will start using SWAP which is a part of the hard disk

A memory leak means that the memory that is no more needed is not getting released

- Possible reasons for making the computer slow:
 - o Disable the not needed programs
 - o Make scheduled restarts
 - o Reduce the sizes of the files being used by a program or the operating system like deleting some logs using “logrotate”
 - o Old hard drive that has started to produce errors
 - o Malicious software
- To know how fast a website is getting loaded you can use a tool called “ab” which stands for “ApacheBench”
- And if we find that the website is slow, we can renice some processes to give the website a higher priority or kill some processes or reorder the execution of the processes.
- Some tools to check linux performance (uptime, dmesg | tail, vmstat 1, mpstat -p ALL 1, pidstat 1, iostat -xz 1, free -m, sar -n DEV 1, sar -n TCP,ETCP 1, top)
- <https://brendangregg.com> check this website for good tools and other stuff.

When writing code, we need to keep few things in mind:

- We should always start by writing clear code that does what it should and only try to make it faster if we realize that it's not fast enough. Trying to optimize every second out of a script is probably not worth your time. If we want our code to finish faster, we need to make our computer do less work.
- A **profiler** is a tool that measures the resources that our code is using, giving us a better understanding of what's going on. For example: use “gprof” to analyze a C program and “cprofile” to analyze a Python program
- Expensive operations include parsing a file, reading data over the network or iterating through a whole list.
- Lists in python have different names in other languages it is called ArrayList in Java, Vector in C++, Array in Ruby, and Slice in Go.
- Dictionaries in python have different names in other languages HashMap in Java, Unordered Map in C++, Hash in Ruby, and Map in Go.
- As a rule of thumb for data structures: if you need to access elements by position or will always iterate through all the elements, use a list to store them. On the other side if we need to look up elements using a key, we will use a dictionary.
- When working with loops try to do the following:
 - o Make the expressions inside the loop as simple as possible
 - o Include in the lists and dictionaries only the needed data nothing extra
 - o Break out of the loop once you have found what you have found what you are looking for.

- To check the time a script takes to execute: we can use the “time” command, the result of it:
 - o Real: the amount of actual time that it took to execute the command.
 - o User for the time spent on the processes in the user space.
 - o Sys: for the time spent on the processes in the system lower than the user space.
- Another profiler is “pprofile3” which generates a file that could be opened using “kcachegrind” which is a GUI to open these files.
- **Concurrency** is a field of computer science dedicated for how we write programs that runs operations in parallel
- One easy way to run **operations** in parallel is to split them into many **processes**.
 - o **Threads**: let us run multiple tasks inside a process.
 - o To implement threading, we can use the “threading” or “asynio” to do that.
 - o If your script is “I/O bound” it does not make sense to split your script into many processors, but if it is “CPU bound” it does.
- When looking for creating a listing service, start by creating a CSV file then put it into a hard drive that is connected to a database and to get it work fast connect the database to a “memcached” that uses RAM to get things run faster.
- And in case of creating a webservice and the server get slow try the following:
 - o Add a caching service like “varnish”
 - o Split the service and use a load balancer
 - o Or instead, you can use the cloud

Dealing with complex slow systems:

- Find the bottleneck, and for that you need to have a good monitoring infrastructure.
- If you have a database issue, try indexing the database and if it does not work try caching the database server or distributing the servers and using a load balancer
- If still slow distribute even more and add more computers
- And after that edit the code if it still not working

- When writing a distributed program and using the “concurrent” module. We need:
 - **Executor**: this is the process that's in charge of distributing the work among the different workers.
 - The **futures module** provides a couple of different executors, one for using threads and another for using processes.

Programs hat crash:

- When a system crash try different things and stop and isolate multiple things to narrow the scope of the problem until you find the root cause, starting from hardware going to software

- When a program crash the first thing to do is to look into the logs
- To find the root cause of a crashing application, you will want to look at all available logs, figure out what changed trace the system or library calls the program makes and create the smallest possible reproduction case.
- To check the possible reasons for a program to crash and you cannot change the code, do the following:
 - o Check the input data type.
 - o Check the compatibility with other services and use a wrapper if you find that one is missing.
 - o Look if the overall system environment is running well with the application. And you can use a container or VM to fix it.
- Wrapper is a function or program that provides a compatibility layer between two functions or programs so they can work well together.
- You can create a watchdog to check if the program is running and if it is not, it will start it again. And it is most useful when availability matters the most.

- Working around “500: internal server error”:
 - o Look up logs
 - o Use “netstat” command to look up the network
 - o Then follow the clues step by step to get to the problem, maybe it will end up as an owner authorization or something that simple.
- The /etc directory will contain the application folder that stores configuration files.

- Accessing invalid memory: happens when an application accesses memory portions that are not assigned to it, and it will result something like segmentation-fault, and it usually happens with low level language like C or C++, when a pointer gets the wrong memory address. So use a debugger to find such errors.
- Getting the PDB file of the binary distro of the application is important for debugging.
- Accessing invalid memory sometimes leads to “undefined behavior” which means the code is doing something that is not valid in the programming language, and to find invalid operations use “valgrind” or “Dr.Memory”

- When you have a bug in your code you can use a debugging tool like “pdb” or “print debugging”
- Use the “logging module” to notify users when an error occurs.

- To understand others code read the code comments and tests then start fixing the bad function and add comments and tests

- Core files store all the information related to the crash so that we or someone else can debug what's going on.
- “gdb” is a tool to run core files and show where the errors have happened
- The backtrace command can be used to show a summary of the function calls that were used to the point where the failure occurs.

- When you are working on a problem document everything so you can keep working on everything clearly, in addition to the people working on resolving the problem and finding the root causes there must be a person who leads the communications between the users affected from the problem and the technicians working on the solution, another person that needs to be there is Incident Commander or Incident Controller needs to look at the big picture and decide what's the best use of the available resources.
- The most important information that you'll want to include in your documentation are:
 - o the root cause.
 - o how you diagnose the problem and found that root cause.
 - o what you did to fix the issue.
 - o what needs to be done to prevent the problem from happening again.
- **Postmortems** are documents that describe details of incidents to help us learn from our mistakes. usually document:
 - o what happened, why it happened.
 - o how it was diagnosed.
 - o how it was fixed.
 - o What we can do to avoid the same event happening in the future.

Most important thing is to remember to make the document helpful in understanding the fix not the problem.

Managing computer resources:

- **Memory leak** happens when a chunk of memory that is no longer needed is not released. And it causes different kinds of failures, delays, and the system start acting in weird ways.
- Memory gets managed by the developer directly in languages like C and C++ while in languages like Python, Java, Go the language itself manages the memory for us.
- Some languages manage memory by reserving the memory, use it and then run the garbage collector, but even if the language itself takes care of memory for us we could still have memory leaks, and for that we need a profiler according to the language being used:
 - o For C and C++ we use “valgrind”
 - o For python use “memory-profiler” or “guppy” or “mprof”
- **Disk leak:**

- When the main part of the space is being taken by applications we can delete some of them and solve the problem.
- Disk leak happens when we check the space taken by different directories and find that the logs and temporary files are the ones taking the biggest part, which could be caused by an error in a configuration file that keep writing logs with each retry failure, and temporary files are the ones gets used by an application and does not get deleted for a failure.
- **Network saturation:**
- The two most important measures for the network are:
 - o Latency: the delay between sending a byte of data from one point and receiving it on the other
 - o Bandwidth: how much data can be sent or received in a second
- Use the command “iftop” to see how much data each connection is sending over the network
- **traffic shaping:** This is a way of marking the data packets sent over the network with different priorities. To avoid having huge chunks of data, use all the bandwidth.
- **Dealing with memory leaks:** we can use for that a tool called “uxterm” We've configured this terminal to have a long scroll buffer. which is that nifty feature that lets us scroll up and see the things that we executed and their output.

- **For time management:** while working in It you may use Eisenhower Decision Matrix where tasks get split into (urgent, important) and if a task is not important do not work on it at all, so always work on important tasks and prioritize according to urgency
- **Technical debt** is the pending work that accumulates when we choose a quick-and-easy solution instead of applying a sustainable long-term one.
- When estimating time used in tasks compare the tasks to the similar tasks you have done before.
- **Network attached storage (NAS):** is a kind of storage that can be attached to your server for additional disk space.
- After providing short-term solutions all the work gets back to normal. You need to start working on long-term solutions and that happens by using a monitoring system, where you can start by monitoring the basics like CPU, memory, disk, and network usage, later you can add other indicators like heat sensors.
- When you are fixing a bug in your own program, write a test that catches the bug so it will never happen again
- **Canary software deployment:** the practice of making staged releases.

Course5:

- Things to be learned in this course:
 - o Scale
 - o Configuration management
 - o Infrastructure as code

- Puppet (a configuration management tool)
- Being able to **scale** what we do means that we can keep achieving larger impacts with the same amount of effort, and a scalable system is a flexible one
- **Unmanaged configuration** is when everything in the computer gets managed manually, in contrast **managed configuration**, is some type of configuration centralization which gets improved even more with automation, also some of the configuration management systems have an error correction capability. Some configuration management tools are Puppet, Chef, Ansible, and CFEngine.
- **Infrastructure as Code(IaC)**: is when all the configuration necessary to deploy and manage a node in the infrastructure is stored in version control. And having everything stored in your system can make it easy for you to deploy a new machine if something goes wrong. So, it brings **consistency**
- Managing your Infrastructure as Code means that your fleet of nodes are consistent, versioned, reliable, and repeatable. Instead of being seen as precious or unique, machines are treated as replaceable resources that can be deployed on-demand through the automation and that principle is called Treating computers like "cattle instead of pets"
- The puppet setup consists of "puppet agent" and "puppet master"
- In puppet, **resources** are the basic unit for modeling the configuration that we want to manage. Such as: "file", "package", and for each resource we can configure different attributes, like: "ensure", "content", "replace".
- We can use "class" in puppet to group a few resources together by grouping related resources together, we can more easily understand the configuration and make changes in the future.
- In puppet we call the "package manager" a "provider"
- To broaden the capabilities of puppet we can use domain specific languages with puppet and that enables us to use variables, statements, functions, which is a declarative language in contrast to python which is a procedural language, A declarative language defines the goal; a procedural language defines the steps to achieve a goal.
- Puppet facts are variables that represent the characteristics of the system. And we can add custom facts, and the facts variable is equivalent to a dictionary in python
- An important aspect of
- configuration management is that
- operations should be **idempotent**. Which means an action can be performed over and over again, without changing the system after the first time the action was performed, and with no unintended side effects.
- In puppet the test and repair paradigm mean We should only take actions when testing determines they need to be done to reach the requested state.
- Another important characteristic of puppet is that it is **stateless**, which means that there's no state being kept between runs of the agent. Each Puppet run is independent of the previous one, and the next one.
- After running a command of puppet, you may find the word **catalog** used which means: The catalog is the list of rules that are generated for one specific computer once the server has evaluated all variables, conditionals, and functions.

- A file has the extension “.pp” is called a “manifest”
- part of Puppet syntax. We write resource types in lowercase when declaring them, but capitalize them when referring to them from another resource's attributes.
- In a puppet class when you use different resources and these resources are dependent on each other such as installing a service and then running it, this dependence is called **resource relationships**. Like “require” and “notify”
- In puppet, a module is a collection of manifests and associated data. Such as manifests, files (.conf files), templates.
- The **files folder** in a module will contain files that won't need to be changed like configuration files.
- metadata.json file of a Puppet module contains additional data about the module often takes the form of installation and compatibility information.
- a **node** is any system where we can run a Puppet agent. Sometimes we want different configurations on different machines, so we define different nodes one node for each type of machine. And each node gets defined by its **FQDNs** and that is short for “fully qualified domain names”
- Nodes definitions are stored in a file called “**site.pp**” where this file is not a part of any module it is on its own in the root of the node environment.
- Puppet works as follows:
 - o The agent generates facts
 - o The agent sends the facts to the master
 - o The master processes the manifests
 - o The master sends the catalog to the agent
- Puppet use “public key infrastructure (**PKI**)” to establish secure connections between the clients, and the technology used by puppet is called “secure socket layer (**SSL**)”
- SSL includes creating two secure keys, one is **private** get saved on the machine and the other is **public** gets shared with all other machines. And through it the node could validate its identity.
- You can configure the server to sign the certificates manually or you can automate the process
- To automate the signing process, use the “puppet config set” command.
- When connecting two machines you need to secure the connection between them.
- The certificate authority (CA) either queues a certificate request for manual validation, or uses pre-shared data to verify before sending the certificate to the agent. The Certificate Authority creates an SSL key for the agent machine and creates a certificate request.
- the first thing that happens after a node connects to the Puppet master for the first time The node requests a certificate.

- When modifying and testing manifests do the following:
 - o Use the “puppet parser validate” command to check your edits for syntax errors
 - o Run the rule with the “--noop” parameter to simulate the operation
 - o Use “puppet-lint” to check the style of the puppet file.
 - o Use test VM instead of production ones
 - o Use the “rspec test” which is like “pytest” for python

- When pushing the changes to production environment, try pushing the changes in batches to avoid having a big failure in case of something goes wrong, and the first machines that adopt the changes are called “canary” just like the canary the miners use to detect poisonous gasses

- **Software as a Service or SaaS** is when a Cloud provider delivers an entire application or program to the customer.
- **Platform as a Service or PaaS** is when a Cloud provider offers a preconfigured platform to the customer.
- **Infrastructure as a Service or IaaS** is when a Cloud provider supplies only the bare-bones computing experience. Some of its providers, amazon EC2, google compute engine, Microsoft azure compute. And another example is qwiklabs.
- When you set cloud services you need to consider **regions and zones** to take care of latency.
- **Capacity** is how much the service can deliver. And it can be measured in disk size, QPS, bandwidth.
- Increasing and decreasing capacity can be called scaling, and the process may be called upscaling and downscaling respectively, and there are different ways of scaling, “horizontally” and “vertically”
- Horizontal scaling could happen by adding more nodes to the service node pool
- Vertical scaling means using bigger nodes, such as a 100GB disk instead of a 10GB disk.

- Another aspect you might need to consider is whether you will make automatic or manual scaling
- Using **automatic scaling** means this service uses metrics to automatically increase or decrease the capacity of the system.
- **Manual scaling** means that changes are controlled by humans instead of software.
- It is preferable to use automatic scaling to avoid sudden increases in demand for a service.

- When we use software as a service that means what is offered fulfills your needs and you only want to control the operation of the software.
- When using the PaaS, you will be able to choose a specific platform requirements but will not have to maintain and monitor the platform daily, and another way of PaaS are managed web applications here you only care about writing the code for the web app. For example, Amazon Elastic Beanstalk, Microsoft App Service, and Google App Engine.
- If the software offered by the cloud provider is not fulfilling, we can use platform as a service or infrastructure as a service.
- When choosing a cloud provider, it is important to check the security of your data and how it is going to be kept.
- Some certifications like SOC 1, ISO 27001, you need to look for to make sure that your provider has invested in security or leave it to the security professionals
- When you are migrating to the cloud and want to use IaaS there are some strategies to do that:

- Just like Lift and shift which means you physically relocate the servers, you can lift you servers and migrate them to the cloud then virtualize the configuration
- **Containers** are applications that are packaged together with their configuration and dependencies.
- Cloud types:
 - Public Clouds: The Cloud services provided to you by a third party.
 - Private Clouds: when your company owns the services and the rest of your infrastructure, whether that's on-site or in a remote data center.
 - Hybrid Clouds: a mixture of both public and private Clouds.
 - Multi-Clouds: a mixture of public and/or private Clouds across vendors.

- When creating a VM in the cloud we need to choose the following:
 - Name
 - Region
 - Zone
 - Machine type, the resources like RAM and CPU
 - Boot disk which is used to determine which OS will run on the VM
 -
- **Reference images** store the contents of a machine in a reusable format,
- **Templating** is the process of capturing all the system configuration to let us create VMS in a repeatable way.
- **A disk image** is a snapshot of a virtual machine's disk at a given point in time.

- When using the cloud web interface, an easy way to create a virtual machine identical to the one we've just configured is to copy and reuse the command line from the bottom of the page.
- `etc/systemd/system/` is the default systemd directory in many Linux distros, including Red Hat Linux.
- From the cloud web UI, you can create a disk snapshot or a reference image. And we can use the reference image to create a VM template

- Another way is to use google cloud from the local computer command line and begin by “gcloud init” command. And it could be helpful when working at scale.

- When deploying at scale we can use a load balancer.
- **load balancer:** ensures that each node receives a balanced number of requests. Some load balancer strategies are:
 - Round robin, and it works by giving each node one request
 - always selecting the same node for requests coming from the same origin,
 - selecting the node that's closest to the requester,
 - selecting the one with the least current load.

- **autoscaling** allows the service to increase or reduce capacity as needed while the service owner only pays for the cost of the machines that are in use at any given time.
- When setting up a website you could use the following structure:
 - o Entry point
 - o Load balancer
 - o Web cache like “varnish” and “nginx” also some caching as a service “cloudflare”, “fastly”
 - o Backend:
 - Load balancer
 - Web servers: generate the actual web content
 - Database: and there may be a separate layer of DB cache and a load balancer for the caching instances, like memcached and redis
- And to the side of the system above we need to use monitoring and alerting
- **Orchestration** is the automated configuration and coordination of complex IT systems and services. Cloud orchestration tools such as Terraform and AWS cloudformation
- To be able to orchestrate the configuration of the overall system needs to be automatically repeatable many tools use the cloud provider API to do that.
- By using orchestration, we could set up monitoring easily and quickly
- Resources/ infrastructure as code: using special machine-readable config files to automate configuration management. which is useful in cases like:
 - o Let's us manage large-scale solutions with a small team.
 - o We can very quickly have an idea of what the deployment looks like, by looking at the configuration.
 - o We can try new things out and roll back if anything goes wrong.
 - o We can look at the history of changes to figure out why a specific change was made
- Some examples of infrastructure as code:
 - o Amazon has Cloud Formation,
 - o Google has Cloud Deployment Manager,
 - o Microsoft has Azure Resource Manager,
 - o OpenStack has Heat Orchestration Templates.
- Similar to “puppet” we can use “Terraform” by using it we can manage the cloud infrastructure, terraform use the cloud API to accomplish the configuration management on different cloud providers and it has its own Domain-specific language

- Nodes in the cloud has two types:
 - o long-lived and their contents need to be periodically updated, like internal mail servers or documentation servers, and these nodes can be managed by puppet
 - o short-lived and updates are made by deleting the old instances and deploying new ones. These nodes get configured by puppet only once and disconnected and nothing more

- **Data storage in the cloud** choosing data storage type depends on:
 - o how much data you want to store,

- what kind of data that is,
- what geographical locations you'll be using it in,
- whether you're mostly writing or reading the data,
- how often the data changes,
- what your budget is
- Some cloud storage technologies are:
 - Block storage: almost exactly like a hard drive and it has two types:
 - Persistent used for instances that are long lived and need to keep data across reboots and upgrades.
 - Ephemerals are used for instances that are only temporary, and only need to keep local data while they're running. Useful when working with containers

To share data across instances you can use some shared file system solutions like NFS or CIFS

- Object storage: let's you place and retrieve objects in a storage bucket. These objects are commonly called blobs, the buckets have names and to interact with these buckets we use APIs
- Database as a service and it has two types:
 - SQL: also called relational and accessed by a query language
 - NOSQL: designed to be distributed across so many machines and accessed fast but to access it need to use an API provided by the database
- Also need to choose the **storage class**:
 - performance, is affected by
 - throughput, is the amount of data that you can read and write in a given amount of time.
 - IOPS, or Input/Output Operations Per Second measures how many reads or writes you can do in one second, no matter how much data you're accessing.
 - Latency, the amount of time it takes to complete a read or write operation. **Read latency** is sometimes reported as the time it takes a storage system to start delivering data after a read request has been made, also known as time to first byte. While **write latency** is typically measured as the amount of time it takes for a write operation to complete.
 - availability,
 - how often the data is accessed
- Hot data is accessed frequently and stored in hot storage while cold data is accessed infrequently and stored in cold storage. Hot storage is SSD.
- **Load balancing**: some techniques are:
 - Round-robin DNS: here you configure all the machines IP addresses in the pool are configured in the DNS server, and when the client tries to access the service, it will try one machine and if it fails it goes to the next address.
 - Sticky sessions: means all requests from the same client always go to the same back-end server.
- Load balancers can do health checks

- When using load balancers to ensure that the client connect to the server close to them you can use “GeoDNS” and “GeoIP”
- Some providers make it their job to bring the service to the user as close as possible content delivery networks or CDNs. They make up a network of physical hosts that are geographically located as close to the end user as possible.

Change management: to make changes safe and secure we need to make sure it is well tested

- Unit tests
- Integration test

continuous integration CI system will build and test our code every time there's a change. Like jenkins and travisCI

Once the change has been committed, the CI system will build and test the resulting code. Now you can use **continuous deployment, or CD**, to automatically deploy the results of the build or build artifacts.

A/B testing, some requests are served using one set of code and configuration, A, and other requests are served using a different set of code and configuration, B.

- When dealing with storage you need to consider **limitations and quotas**, such as there is a limited number of disk writes per minutes to a blob, or **rate limits** to prevent the service from overloading the whole system, **utilizations limits** cap the total amount of a certain resource that you can provision
- And in case you are dealing with one of the above you can request a quota increase from the provider
- monitoring is important:
 - When an error is generated when trying to access the server it could be:
 - o **In the range of 500** which means it was generated inside of the server while generating the response.
 - o **In the 400 range** means there was a client-side problem in the request.
 - Some monitoring systems like AWS Cloudwatch, Google Stack Driver, or Azure Metrics are offered directly by the Cloud providers.
 - Other systems like Prometheus, Datadog, or Nagios can be used across vendors.
 - There are two models of monitoring systems:
 - o Pull model: which means that the monitoring infrastructure periodically queries our service to get the metrics.
 - o push model, which means that our service needs to periodically connect to the system to send the metrics.
 - **Pro tip**, you only want to store the metrics that you care about, since storing all these metrics in the system takes space, and storage space costs money.
 - **Whitebox monitoring** checks the behavior of the system from the inside.

- **Blackbox monitoring** checks the behavior of the system from the outside.

- To schedule monitoring and alerts in linux we could use “cron”, raising an alert means something needs human intervention.
- Alerts that need an immediate attention are called pages and they get send through a **pager** and pages may come in different forms
- All alerts should be **actionable**. If you get a bug or a page and there's nothing for you to do, then the alert isn't **actionable**, and it should be changed, or it shouldn't be there at all. Otherwise, it is just **noise**
- **Service level objectives, or SLOs**, are pre-established performance goals for a specific service. And it needs to be:
 - o **Measurable**: a five 9 service means 99.999% of the time the service is available. And a five 9 service is expensive and requires a big team to maintain
- **service level agreements, or SLAs**. is a commitment between a provider and a client.
- Some providers use an error budget to manage their services, which means the amount of down time the service may have before it needs to be fixed, for example, a service that has three nines of availability. This means the service can be down 43 minutes per month.
- **Stackdriver** is a monitoring tool that works well
- An **Alerting Policy** specifies the conditions that trigger alerts, and the actions to be taken when these alerts are triggered, like sending an email address notification.
- The response code in the server's message is the part from part of an HTTP message from a web server that is useful for tracking the overall status of the response and can be monitored and logged.

- When you have a problem, after an upgrade first way to solve it is by rolling back to the well-functioning version, then take a disk image of one of the problematic machines and put it on a healthy machine to analyze it.
- Create a debugging machine inside the network before any problems happen.
- When buying a service from a cloud provider you need to know where the provider keeps the logs, errors and other debugging related stuff. To use them to debug the problematic machines.
- When we are not sure if the error is caused on our side or on the provider's side you can try the following to debug the issue.
 - o Change the region of your service to find whether it's the provider's fault. If it fails everywhere then it's probably the service's fault
 - o If you have some resources issues you can move your service to a bigger machine and test whether it is faulty or just big
 - o You can rollback to older well-functioning versions.
 - o If you having a problem with a software installed on a container you can install it on another container and check if the issue happens there too.

- If you operate a service that stores any kind of data, it's critical that you implement automatic backups and that you periodically check that those backups are working correctly by performing restores. Not only for the data but also for the infrastructure and code.
- And for better reliability results you need to have two of almost everything (redundancy) like the infrastructure, service, data, network connection all up and running in order if something goes wrong it takes the load and the service keeps running. Even on a data center or cloud provider level you still need redundancy.
- HTTP response classes:
 - Informational responses (100–199)
 - Successful responses (200–299)
 - Redirects (300–399)
 - Client errors (400–499)
 - Server errors (500–599)